

EARTH SCIENCES

DIGITAL MODELING OF MAGNETIC ANOMALIES

İsgandarov E.,

Associate professor,

Department of "Geophysics" Azerbaijan State Oil and Industrial University (ASOIU), Azerbaijan, Baku

Novruzov A.

Master student,

Department of "Geophysics" Azerbaijan State Oil and Industrial University (ASOIU), Azerbaijan, Baku

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Abstract

The article is devoted to numerical modeling of magnetic anomalies, the solution of which plays an important role in the geological interpretation of the observed anomalies in magnetometry. The object of study is the Zardab uplift, in the section of which Mesozoic volcanic-sedimentary deposits take part, which are well displayed in a magnetic field. Using modern graphical tools such as SURFER and the software developed at the Department of Geophysics for processing and interpreting gravimetric and magnetic anomalies, 2D and 3D maps of the surface of Mesozoic deposits, maps of the local magnetic field of the Zardab area were calculated and built, which gives the most complete spatial and areal representation of nature magnetic and gravitational anomalies

Keywords: modeling, structural model, magnetic model, digital modeling, digitization, local magnetic anomaly.

Introduction

In prospecting, exploration and study of the geological structure of prospective oil and gas and ore-bearing areas, the magnetometric method of exploration is of great importance, which is based on studying the nature of the distribution of magnetic fields created by individual structural uplifts, which have magnetic properties of its constituent rocks. At the stage of quantitative interpretation of magnetic data, a very important task is solved - modeling of magnetometric anomalies, which is of great importance in geological interpretation [2-7]. Interesting modeling methods have been developed for solving direct and inverse problems of gravity and magnetic exploration [1,8]. Currently, this problem is being solved using modern graphic programs in two-dimensional and three-dimensional versions based on the results of computer calculations of theoretical magnetic fields according to the developed algorithms and programs, which provides the most complete idea of the shape, depth and size of the desired geological objects. This explains the relevance of ongoing research in this area. The purpose of this study is the digital modeling of local magnetic anomalies of the Zardab uplift, located in the eastern part of the Middle Kura depression of Azerbaijan and is promising in terms of oil and gas.

Means and methods

Real geological objects that create gravitational and magnetic anomalies can only be likened to regular-shaped bodies only approximately, and therefore the calculated parameters of geological objects in most cases give only the most general idea of their actual sizes. You can refine the parameters of the object by choosing a body whose anomaly coincides with the observed one. By successively changing the shape of the body, one can achieve a close correspondence between the observed and calculated curves. The coincidence of these curves allows us to state that the resulting body

configuration corresponds to the shape of a real geological object. All methods are based on the replacement of the magnetic action of such a body by the action of the sum of bodies of the simplest form, the effect of which can be accurately calculated. With their help, a body of arbitrary shape can easily be divided into elementary figures of the same shape, the gravitational action of which can be accurately calculated using formulas. In this case, the magnetic effect of a body of arbitrary shape is equal to the total effect of all elementary figures contained in the volume of the body. ASOIU has developed GMTEOR FORTRAN program at the Department of Geophysics, which allow calculating the vertical component of the magnetic field from a geological body of arbitrary shape based on the division of the body into elementary prisms and two-dimensional bodies with a rectangular section [2-6]. Digital modeling of structures and gravimagnetic anomalies is currently widely used, as it allows in two-dimensional and three-dimensional versions to more accurately and visually present the geological and geophysical results obtained at the interpretation stage. To implement digital modeling, graphic programs such as SURFER and others are used, which allow you to digitize the results and perform various transformations in order to filter useful information.

The Zardab uplift is located in the northwest of the Zardab-Muradkhanli anticlinal zone in the Muradkhanli oil and gas region [9]. This structure was discovered at the end of the 60s of the last century as a result of seismic exploration (reflected wave method). Analysis and generalization of gravimetric and magnetometric materials were carried out in the field in the 1970s, and high-precision and field research works were carried out in the 1980s (Fig. 1). In 1970, preparatory works for drilling the structure began. In 1972, well was dug to a depth of 4608 meters in the arch part of the structure. Later, another well was dug 2.5 km west of

that well. Technically, this well could not be fully reached to the project depth. Other well, dug to a depth of 4,825 meters, revealed carbonate sediments of the Upper Cretaceous and confirmed the data of seismic exploration. Thus, oil manifestations were recorded in Eocene-Upper Cretaceous sediments in these wells. Although short-term oil flow was obtained in the search well dug in the Zardab field with a production of 350

tons per day, the well was not tested in normal condition later due to strong waterlogging. Volcanogenic-sedimentary deposits of the Mesozoic, which have excessive density and intensity of magnetization, take part in the section of the Zardab uplift. It should be noted that the Zardab uplift was first noted on the maps of local gravity anomalies and magnetic anomalies constructed from gravity and magnetic survey data.

Fig. 1. Structural map of Upper Cretaceous deposits according to data seismic surveys (in units of meters) [9].

At the beginning, digital modeling of the Zardab structure itself was performed. To do this, using the SURFER program in the Digit mode, the isolines of the structural map of the Zardab area were digitized, some of the results of which are shown in Table 1. Then, based on the grid obtained in the mapping mode, the structural map itself was built in 2D and 3D versions, on which the modern interface displays a structural map of the Zardab uplift, the amplitude of which reaches approximately 500m (Fig.2-3).

The models of the magnetic and gravity fields along the two-dimensional profile of the Upper Cretaceous sediments involved in the geophysical section of the serum area were calculated using the GMTEOR

FORTTRAN program (Fig. 4). According to these results, the corresponding V_z and Z curves were constructed in the EXCEL program (Fig. 5-6). As can be seen from the figure, the calculated field is characterized by two gravitational and magnetic maxima. A comparison of these curves with the actual curves shows that there is a reverse magnetization in this area. The amplitude of the magnetic curve reaches 9.6 Gamm. The amplitude of the gravity curve is equal to 2.2 mGal. In the article, the corresponding 2D and 3D local magnetic anomaly maps of the Zerdab area were converted to digital form using the Surfer program (Fig.7-8).

Table 1.

Coordinates and depths of some digitized points isolines

X,inc	Y, inc	Z, m	X	Y	Z
29.96789883	52.50194553	-5100	135.810654	282.3913142	-4500
41.30496109	41.16488327	-5100	146.9582792	264.7409075	-4500
52.64202335	29.82782101	-5100	157.1769357	244.3035946	-4500
59.61867704	19.36284047	-5100	169.2535297	222.9373129	-4500
65.72324903	1.921206226	-5100	184.11703	203.4289688	-4500
33.43542441	114.3787631	-5000	203.6253742	190.423406	-4500
50.49114769	107.2722117	-5000	226.8495934	169.0571243	-4500
68.96818124	91.63779868	-5000	237.9972186	147.6908426	-4500
76.07473261	72.45010999	-5000	239.8551562	121.6797171	-4500
84.60259425	56.81569698	-5000	236.1392811	97.52652908	-4500
87.4452148	41.18128398	-5000	236.1392811	76.16024738	-4500
93.84111103	26.25752611	-5000	253.7896877	50.14912185	-4500
98.10504185	3.516561732	-5000	266.7952505	36.21459031	-4500
32.72476927	170.5205189	-4900	305.8119388	21.35109	-4500
46.93787201	165.5459329	-4900	341.112752	20.42212123	-4500
59.01900933	152.0434853	-4900	368.0528463	33.427684	-4500
73.23211206	140.6730031	-4900	391.2770655	27.85387138	-4500
85.31324939	125.7492452	-4900	383.8453154	18.56418369	-4500
98.81569698	105.1402463	-4900	390.3480968	3.700683384	-4500
110.8968343	86.66321272	-4900	160.8928108	292.6099706	-4400
115.8714203	65.34355862	-4900	157.1769357	274.959564	-4400
122.9779716	41.89193911	-4900	163.6797171	257.3091574	-4400
125.109937	22.70425042	-4900	173.8983735	239.6587508	-4400
132.9271435	2.095251458	-4900	191.5487802	225.7242192	-4400
33.43542441	210.3172065	-4800	216.6309369	202.5	-4400
50.49114769	198.2360692	-4800	242.6420625	195.9972186	-4400
67.54687097	184.7336216	-4800	262.1504066	203.4289688	-4400
81.7599737	174.0737945	-4800	264.9373129	228.5111255	-4400
95.97307644	155.596761	-4800	255.6476252	245.2325634	-4400
113.7394549	137.8303826	-4800	245.4289688	261.0250325	-4400
127.9525576	119.353349	-4800	224.0626871	273.1016265	-4400
138.6123846	99.45500518	-4800	211.9860931	287.9651268	-4400
144.2976257	76.71404081	-4800	197.1225928	295.3968769	-4400
146.4295911	55.39438671	-4800	180.4011549	295.3968769	-4400
147.8509014	34.78538775	-4800	85.64634046	396.6544728	-4400
150.693522	18.4403196	-4800	111.657466	379.9330349	-4400
155.6681079	2.805906595	-4800	143.2424042	372.5012848	-4400
43.38459632	246.5606185	-4700	165.5376546	359.495722	-4400
63.99359529	228.7942401	-4700	190.6198114	340.9163466	-4400
78.20669802	213.8704822	-4700	212.9150618	323.26594	-4400
96.68373157	198.9467243	-4700	233.3523748	309.3314085	-4400
113.7394549	183.3123113	-4700	252.8607189	292.6099706	-4400
132.2164884	160.5713469	-4700	277.9428757	276.8175015	-4400
152.1148322	139.962348	-4700	302.0960637	262.88297	-4400
165.6172798	122.1959696	-4700	321.6044078	255.4512198	-4400

Fig.2. Structural 2D map over the surface of the Upper Cretaceous deposits of the Zardab-Shikhabagi area (in units of meters, according to the results of digital modeling)

Fig.3. Structural 3D map over the surface of the Upper Cretaceous deposits of the Zardab-Shikhabagi area (in units of meters, according to the results of digital modeling)

n	X1	X2	EMAX	DX	DS	Y								
14	-2	8	5,6	0,4	0,2	30								
4,2	4,1	4	3,9	3,8	3,8	3,8	3,8	3,8	3,8	3,8	3,8	3,8	3,8	3,9
4,6	4,6	4,6	4,6	4,6	4,6	4,6	4,6	4,6	4,6	4,6	4,6	4,6	4,6	4,6
N	X	G	ZA											
1	-2	1,1	0,1											
2	-1	1,4	1,8											
3	0	1,6	4,2											
4	1	1,9	6,9											
5	2	2,1	8,9											
6	3	2,2	9,6											
7	4	2,1	8,6											
8	5	1,8	6,2											
9	6	1,6	3,4											
10	7	1,3	1,1											
11	8	1	-0,4											

Fig.4. Calculation results of fields Za and Δg

N	X	G	ZA
1	-2	1,1	0,1
2	-1	1,4	1,8
3	0	1,6	4,2
4	1	1,9	6,9
5	2	2,1	8,9
6	3	2,2	9,6
7	4	2,1	8,6
8	5	1,8	6,2
9	6	1,6	3,4
10	7	1,3	1,1
11	8	1	-0,4

Fig. 5. Comparative form of calculation results

(N is a number of observation points; x is coordinates of observation points in unit of kilometer ; G is Δg values in unit of mGal ; Za is a vertical component of magnetic field in unit of Gamm)

Fig.6. Calculated Δg and Z curves (Zardab area)

Fig.7. 2D representation of magnetic local anomaly Z_{10} map of Zardab area (in units of Gamm)

Fig.8. 3D representation of the magnetic local anomaly Z_{10} map of Zardab area (in units of Gamm)

CONCLUSIONS:

1. A review and analysis of the issues of digital modeling of magnetic anomalies and geological structures based on geophysical survey data has been completed. The importance and effectiveness of the use of digital modeling for solving the main geological problem of magnetic exploration is shown.

2. The structural map of the Zardab-Shikhbagi uplift was digitized using the SURFER graphic program and, based on the resulting grid, a model structural map was built on a computer in 2D and 3D versions, on which the Zardab uplift is distinguished with an amplitude of about 0.5 km, and the Shikhbagi uplift is characterized by an amplitude of 0.8 km.

3. The gravitational magnetic effect was calculated in a two-dimensional version using the GMTEOR FORTRAN- program developed at the Department of Geophysics of ASOIU along the profile of the Zardob structure crossing the Zardab structure, and the curves of gravity and the vertical component of the magnetic field were plotted, on which the Zardab maximum is clearly distinguished.

4. The local magnetic anomaly ΔZ_{10} of the Zardob uplift obtained at the department was digitized and a digital model of this magnetic anomaly was built using a modern interface in 2D and 3D versions, on which the

Zardob local maximum of the magnetic field with an intensity of 2 gamma is more clearly distinguished.

5. The Zardob uplift is promising in terms of oil and gas, it is well displayed in magnetic and gravitational fields, which indicates the volcanic-sedimentary Mesozoic nature of this uplift, and therefore the results of digital modeling are recommended to be taken into account in further geophysical studies.

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